

"ECOLOGY OF SCENIC PLANTS " TOPIC THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING.

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Annotation. In this article, conclusions and recommendations on researching the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching the topic "Ecology of scenic plants" , forming the development of an electronic educational module on the subject, and improving teaching have been developed.

Key words . Heliophytes synophytes hygrophytes xerophyte mesophytes

German scientist E. Haeckel defined the science of ecology. Ecology is a combination of the Greek words *oikos* , which means *house, residence* , and *logos* , which means *study, science* .

Ecology studies the interactions between organisms and their environment. Ecology - provides information about the disruption of connections in nature under the influence of abiotic, biotic and anthropogenic factors. Ecology consists of several disciplines, in which biological sciences are the main ones. Because humans, animals and plants are biological objects that are constantly in contact with each other and the external environment.

Information about the relationship and distribution of plant life with the external environment has been known since ancient times. That is, Theophrastus, who lived in 372-277 AD, and Pliny the Elder, who lived in 23-79 AD, studied the relationship between plants and the environment. Theophrastus determined that the shape and growth of plants depend on climate and soil conditions. He also described the life forms of plants from an ecological point of view.

Abu Ali ibn Sina, who lived in the Middle Ages, studied the morphology, origin of names, composition and geography of medicinal plants and left information about them.

We find ecological data in the works of Mahmud Kashkari, who lived in Eastern Turkestan in the 11th century. His books contain ecological, morphological and geographical information about 200 plants.

We can find botanical and geographical information about the plants of Central Asia in the works of Z. Babur.

In the 19th century, the German naturalist A. Humboldt studied the distribution of plants depending on temperature and gave a classification of their life forms.

In 1895, Warming's book "The spread of plants under the influence of the external environment" was published.

In the 20th century, with the improvement of ecological methods, new ecological factors - day length, the reaction of the soil solution, and the influence of trace elements - began to be studied.

As a result of the increasing influence of anthropogenic factors on nature, the issues studied by ecology are increasing.

VV Dukachev studied the connection of living organisms with the external environment in different geographical zones.

The founder and organizer of ecological observations in Uzbekistan is E.P. Korovin. In the 1930s, he studied the plant community and the environment together.

A part of nature that surrounds organisms and is in constant contact with them is the environment.

The living environment consists of a set of factors necessary for life, without which organisms cannot live. Organisms live in a complex and changing world, and they gradually adapt their lives to it. During evolutionary development, organisms have mastered four main living environments. The first of them is the water environment. Life originated and spread in water. Later, living organisms occupied the atmosphere. Soil is a special living environment. The specific fourth environment of life is the body of a living organism.

Each external environment-ecological factors affecting the life of plants and their distribution on Earth are divided into 3 groups:

1. Abiotic factors:
2. Interactions of biotic factors-organisms.
3. Anthropogenic factors are the effects of human activity.

The external environment usually affects plants in three ways, minimal, optimal, maximal. Each external influence, acting at an optimal level, ensures the normal life of plants.

Depending on their light requirements, 3 main groups of plants differ. These are light-loving plants (heliophytes), shade-loving or shade-growing plants (synophytes) and light-tolerant plants. Light-loving plants grow normally in light conditions affected by the power of sunlight, and are shade-tolerant. Shade-loving or shade-growing plants are optimal in areas with little light, they do not like strong levels of light. This group of plants includes plant species that are distributed in strongly shaded areas. Many indoor and greenhouse plants grown here are shade-loving plants. *Light-loving* plants: tilogoch, togterak, birch are light-loving trees. *Shade-loving* plants grow well in the open.

50-90 percent of the plant body is water.

Depending on the water needs of plants, they are divided into hydrophytes, hygrophytes, mesophytes and xerophytes. *Hydrophytes* are plants that grow in water. Examples of hydrophytes are white nymphia and water lily (*Zupha luteum*). Plants belonging to *hygrophytes* prefer moist soils and are very resistant to drought. *Xerophytic* plants grow in dry and humid lands. For example, anabasis bush, yulgun, saxovul, sugarcane, etc. are xerophytic plants. Plants belonging to *mesophytes* grow in moderately moist soils. Mesophytes include red oak, common purple, common sorghum, green sorghum, manchurian walnut, Siberian sycamore, alder, spruce, etc.

A.P. Shennikov includes species adapted to warm and cold climatic conditions of northern latitudes and high mountain zones to psychrophytes, and species adapted to dry and cold climatic conditions of high mountains to cryophytes.

Air is one of the necessary factors for plant life. Plants have oxygen with breath takes, and carbon dioxide gas is organic matter synthesis for is spent. Carbon dioxide in the air is released from the air gases that occur. For example, industry in the centers of the Mir is used as a result sulfur gas is separated. What is it? It is to plants much harmful effect is enough. Of the pineapples European spruce, common pine; Among deciduous trees, spruce, oak, beech and birch are especially resistant to the effects of this gas. Thorny spruce, hemlock, camellia, poplar, purple, elm, maple and yellow acacia are partially tolerant.

Wind can have different effects on plants. The winged fruit and hairy seeds of many plants, such as maple, willow, and gorse, are dispersed by wind.

Soil plays an important role in the life of plants. Soil can be fertile or infertile. Megatrophic plants that grow on fertile soil include sharp-leaf maple, spruce, field maple, larch, larch, white and brittle willows, hemlock, walnut, and others.

The effects of plants on plants vary widely. Their direct and indirect effects are different.

The interaction between animals and plants occurs through the food chain. The direct effect of animals is manifested in pollination and spreading of fruits and seeds, fertilization of the land with manure.

The role of people in the life of plants is huge. Usually, people affect plants for a purpose (for their own benefit), but it is not always beneficial.

It can be concluded that plants are affected by external factors at the same time, but their responses are different. That is the importance of studying them.

In accordance with the national program of personnel training of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is envisaged to provide educational institutions with specially trained pedagogical personnel, to create an environment based on competition in their work process, to provide the educational process with quality educational literature and advanced pedagogical technologies.

Implementation of these tasks is the direct duty of each educational institution. Successful implementation of pedagogical technologies in the educational process requires that each subject teacher has special knowledge and skills, as well as methodological training necessary for pedagogical practice.

Education does not accept the influence of all active and slow changes, but it has its influence on what is happening in society. From this point of view, changes in education are not only a result, but a condition for the future development of society.

Currently, the wide application of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development. Special attention is being paid to the systematic introduction of innovations into the field of education at the same time when the scope of pedagogical innovations is increasing and the modernization process is developing rapidly in the country. But despite the fact that many pedagogical innovations are being created, the level of introduction of pedagogical research on the implementation of new content, forms, methods and tools of teaching in educational processes cannot be considered sufficient.

The following innovations and educational technologies are used in the education of ornamental plants of Uzbekistan today in developed foreign countries.

Technology of educational activities	Int e rfaol M e tods	Graphic Organization e r
1. Lectures and educational technology . 2. C e minar training educational technology . 3. Practical training educational technology . 4. Independent educational technology. 5. Case - stadium educational technology . 6. Project educational technology	1. Brainstorming. 2. Free writing. 3. Reasoned essay. 4. FSMU. 5. Blitz -s package. 6. Blitz is a game. 7. Training manual. 8. Written and oral roundtable discussion. 9. Definition of concepts. 10. Compose a text based on concepts. 11. A sequence of confused logical chains	1. Clast e r. 2. B-B-B drawing 3. T- drawing. 4. Venn diagram. 5. Conceptual table. 6. Insert table. 7. "Why" diagram 8. "How?" diagram 9. Fish skeleton. 10. Classification table. 11. Lily flower

Effective teaching technologies:

- * problem teaching;
- * technologies that develop critical thinking;
- * developing educational technologies;
- * game technologies;
- * collaborative technologies;
- * differentiated and individual technology of teaching;
- * computer-information technologies.

It is known that the application of innovations and advanced foreign experiences in the process of teaching "Biology" in the higher educational institutions of our country is one of the urgent issues of today.

First of all in science news what What is innovation in science ? said to questions answer to give it is necessary Today's in the day in practice news and innovation words between differences there is News this in science the most last achievements , knowledge , methods is counted.

LIST OF REFERENCES :

1. Pechenits yn V.P., i dr. Culture is better . - Tashkent . : " Shar q" , 2005 .
2. Nabiev M.M., Kazakbaev R.Yu. Oprelitel dekorativnyx derevev i Kustarnikov to Uzbekistan. - T. : " SCIENCE " , 1975 .
3. "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent: "Chinor ENK", 2009.
5. Kravchenko L.K. Landscape herbaceous plants. - Tashkent, 1971.
6. Kravchenko L.K. Tsvetochno-decorative plants. - Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan", 1973.
7. Khamidov A. Geography of plants. - Tashkent.: "Teacher", 1984.
8. Prator O', Jumaev K. Systematics of higher plants. - Tashkent, 2003.